

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

UPHOLDING ACADEMIC EXCELLENCE: PRACTICES FOR ENSURING ACADEMIC INTEGRITY IN ASYNCHRONOUS MODE

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Abstract

The COVID-19 pandemic and subsequent shift to online learning presented challenges for educators worldwide, including in Ukraine. This paper examines the transition to asynchronous instruction as a means to address disruptions caused by the pandemic and subsequent war. The focus is on upholding academic integrity in this new mode of teaching. The study explores the importance of academic integrity in asynchronous teaching, the challenges it presents, and strategies to foster and maintain integrity. The paper emphasizes the need for original assignments that align with learning outcomes, assessments that demand higher-order thinking skills, the use of randomization features in assessments, establishing clear expectations and consequences, and promoting collaboration among students. By implementing these practices, instructors can create a learning environment that upholds the values of integrity, fosters ethical behavior, and empowers students to take pride in their own academic achievements.

Keywords: academic integrity, asynchronous instruction, online learning, original assignments, higher-order thinking skills, randomization, expectations, consequences, collaboration, ethical behavior.

Introduction.

The COVID-19 pandemic posed significant challenges for the education sector, prompting a sudden shift to online learning without sufficient preparation. This transition exposed the digital readiness of educators and learners globally, including in Ukraine. Instead of well-designed and pre-planned online learning scenarios, educators had to rely on improvisation and ad hoc strategies, leading to various predicaments (Rapanta et al., 2020).

Following the easing of the emergency state, the education community entered a post-pandemic phase, allowing educators to selectively incorporate effective solutions into well-designed online scenarios while refining or discarding ineffective practices [7]. However, in 2022, the education system in Ukraine faced a new challenge: the outbreak of war. This conflict introduced additional complications, such as airstrikes, power cuts, and rolling blackouts, which disrupted synchronous online classes and hindered students' access to education at a national level. Consequently, educators had to address these emerging obstacles to prevent gaps in the educational process, leading to reconsideration and adaptation of synchronous online class strategies, approaches, and methods to the new circumstances. This necessitated the pivotal adoption and integration of asynchronous instruction mode.

Problem statement.

In the realm of higher education, the shift towards asynchronous teaching modes, facilitated by online platforms and Learning Management Systems (LMS), has brought about numerous opportunities for both instructors and students. However, this transition has also posed new challenges, particularly in upholding academic integrity. Academic integrity, encompassing

principles of honesty, fairness, and ethical conduct, lies at the core of the educational process and ensures the credibility and validity of learning outcomes. As universities adopt asynchronous teaching modes, it becomes imperative to recognize and address the unique considerations and strategies required to foster and maintain academic integrity in this context (Wiley, 2022).

The importance of upholding academic integrity in asynchronous teaching modes cannot be overstated. In these settings, students engage in learning activities and assessments at their own pace and time, without direct supervision or immediate interaction with instructors or peers. While this flexibility promotes independent learning and accommodates diverse student needs, it also presents opportunities for academic misconduct, such as plagiarism, cheating, or unauthorized collaboration (Awdry, R., & Ives, B., 2022; Burgason et al., 2019). Asynchronous teaching modes demand proactive measures to prevent and detect these violations, ensuring the fairness and authenticity of students' work, as well as the integrity of the educational process.

Aim of research.

Drawing upon recent scholarly research and shared experiences within the educational community, our study embarks on a comprehensive exploration of a critical area of inquiry: the facilitation of academic integrity in the context of asynchronous instruction. Therefore, the purpose of this paper is to present our research findings and solutions, which establish essential prerequisites for the effective implementation of asynchronous teaching methods.

Findings.

Promoting Academic Integrity through Original Assignments. To effectively promote academic integrity, it is crucial for instructors to avoid relying on pre-existing assignments or materials that are easily accessible online. When students encounter assignments that can be found with a quick internet search, the temptation to engage in academic dishonesty may increase. By eschewing pre-existing materials, instructors can reduce the likelihood of students resorting to cheating and encourage them to engage more authentically with the learning process. Instead, instructors should design assignments that are unique, tailored to the specific learning objectives, and aligned with the course content (Hamilton, 2007; Bretag, 2018).

Original assignments can take various forms in asynchronous language teaching. For example, instructors can create case studies that require students to propose solutions based on their language skills. Another approach is to assign open-ended projects that allow students to explore a topic of interest, conduct independent research, and present their findings in a creative format, such as a multimedia presentation or a written report. By designing assignments that encourage students to think independently, apply their knowledge, and demonstrate their understanding in novel ways, instructors not only promote academic integrity but also foster a deeper engagement with the subject matter (Burgason et al., 2019; Lathrop, 2000).

Moreover, the creation of original assignments provides an opportunity for instructors to align the assessments with the specific learning outcomes of the course. By tailoring assignments to address the desired language skills and competencies, instructors can ensure that students are actively engaged in the learning process and that the assessments accurately measure their progress. This alignment between assignments and learning outcomes helps students understand the purpose and relevance of their work, further motivating them to approach the assignments with integrity and a commitment to academic excellence.

Promoting Academic Integrity through Original Assignments.

Designing assessments that demand higher-order thinking skills is a powerful strategy to promote academic integrity and deter cheating in asynchronous language teaching (Hamilton, 2007). These assessments move beyond mere recall of information and instead require students to analyze, evaluate, and synthesize information in order to demonstrate their understanding and application of concepts. By engaging students in these cognitive processes, instructors create a learning environment that values critical thinking and discourages academic dishonesty (Bretag, 2018; Comas-Forgas et al., 2021).

Incorporating higher-order thinking assessments challenges students to go beyond surface-level comprehension and delve into deeper levels of understanding. For instance, instead of asking students to simply memorize facts or definitions, instructors can design assessment tasks that require them to analyze complex scenarios, evaluate multiple perspectives, and propose creative solutions. This shift in assessment focus compels

students to engage with the material more meaningfully, as they are required to think critically, reason logically, and apply their knowledge in novel ways.

Promoting Academic Integrity through Fostering Higher-Order Thinking Skills.

By designing assessments that demand higher-order thinking skills, instructors send a clear message to students about the importance of academic integrity. These assessments require students to draw on their own knowledge, skills, and insights, leaving little room for relying on external sources or engaging in dishonest practices. The emphasis on critical thinking and problem-solving not only strengthens students' understanding of the subject matter but also cultivates their ethical behavior and commitment to academic honesty (Holden, 2021; Jenkins et al., 2022).

Moreover, higher-order thinking assessments contribute to the development of essential skills that extend beyond the course content. Students acquire valuable analytical, evaluative, and synthesis abilities, which are highly sought-after in the professional world. By aligning assessments with real-world tasks and challenges, instructors prepare students for future academic and career endeavors, where integrity and critical thinking are paramount (Bretag, 2018).

In conclusion, designing assessments that demand higher-order thinking skills serves as a powerful means to promote academic integrity and discourage cheating in asynchronous language teaching. By engaging students in deep cognitive processes and emphasizing critical thinking, instructors foster a culture of academic integrity, where originality and ethical behavior are valued. These assessments not only enhance students' understanding and retention of the course material but also equip them with essential skills for their future academic and professional success.

Promoting Academic Integrity through Randomization.

Randomizing questions and answers on quizzes and exams using Learning Management System (LMS) features has emerged as a valuable strategy for promoting academic integrity in asynchronous language teaching (Ali, 2011; Golden, 2020). By incorporating randomization, instructors can effectively reduce the incentive for students to share answers, as the likelihood of two students receiving the same questions in the same order diminishes. This approach not only discourages collusion but also enhances the overall validity of assessments by ensuring that students are evaluated based on their comprehension of the subject matter rather than their ability to memorize a specific sequence of questions or answers. Employing these LMS features allows instructors to foster academic integrity and establish a fair and unbiased assessment environment.

The randomization of questions and answers in quizzes and exams serves multiple purposes in promoting academic integrity. Firstly, it mitigates the possibility of students sharing answers during the assessment process. When the order of questions and answer choices is randomized, students cannot rely on their peers for answers, as each individual is likely to encounter a unique set of questions and answer options. This reduction in collaboration opportunities reinforces

the importance of independent thinking and discourages dishonest practices that undermine the integrity of the evaluation process.

Furthermore, the randomization of questions and answers enhances the validity of assessments by emphasizing students' comprehension and application of knowledge. When questions and answer choices are presented in a randomized manner, students are compelled to engage in a deeper understanding of the subject matter, rather than relying on rote memorization or pattern recognition. This approach ensures that assessments accurately gauge students' grasp of the concepts and their ability to analyze and apply their knowledge, aligning with the desired learning outcomes of the course. By emphasizing comprehension and critical thinking, instructors promote academic integrity and reinforce the significance of genuine learning rather than superficial memorization.

By leveraging the capabilities of an LMS, instructors can easily implement randomization features in their assessments. LMS platforms offer options to shuffle the order of questions and answer choices, ensuring that each student encounters a unique arrangement. This technological convenience not only simplifies the implementation process but also supports instructors in creating a fair and unbiased assessment environment, where each student has an equal opportunity to showcase their understanding and skills (Golden, 2020).

In conclusion, the strategic use of randomization in the design of assessments is an effective approach to fostering academic integrity in asynchronous language teaching. By incorporating randomization features provided by Learning Management Systems, instructors can reduce the incentive for collaboration and promote independent thinking among students (Ali, 2011). Moreover, this practice enhances the validity of assessments by emphasizing comprehension and application of knowledge rather than memorization. By implementing randomization, instructors create a fair and unbiased assessment environment, ensuring that each student is evaluated on their own merits.

Promoting Academic Integrity through Establishing Expectations and Consequences.

Establishing clear expectations for academic integrity and outlining the repercussions of academic dishonesty is not only crucial but also an essential aspect of fostering a culture of integrity in asynchronous language teaching (Chiang et.al., 2022). By clearly communicating these expectations and consequences to students, instructors can effectively discourage them from engaging in cheating and unethical practices, while simultaneously cultivating an environment that values academic integrity.

One of the primary ways to promote academic integrity is by clearly articulating expectations for academic honesty. Instructors should communicate their expectations regarding proper citation practices, the use of sources, collaboration, and the submission of original work. By explicitly outlining these expectations, students gain a clear understanding of what is considered acceptable and are more likely to uphold the principles of integrity throughout their academic journey. When students are aware of the importance placed on

academic integrity, they are less likely to be tempted to resort to dishonest practices.

Equally important is the need to inform students about the consequences of academic dishonesty. By explicitly stating the potential repercussions of cheating, such as receiving a failing grade, academic probation, or even disciplinary action, instructors create a strong deterrent against engaging in dishonest behavior. Students are more likely to think twice before succumbing to the temptation of cheating when they understand the serious consequences that may accompany such actions. The fear of negative outcomes can act as a powerful motivator to uphold academic integrity and make ethical choices (Comas-Forgas et al., 2021).

Instructors should also emphasize the significance of academic integrity as an essential aspect of their educational journey. By highlighting the value of honesty, integrity, and the pursuit of knowledge, instructors can instill in students a sense of pride and responsibility in their own academic work. This can be achieved through classroom discussions, assignments that require reflection on the importance of academic integrity, and fostering a supportive and respectful learning environment where academic honesty is celebrated.

Furthermore, instructors should ensure that the consequences for academic dishonesty are consistently enforced. This means being vigilant in detecting instances of cheating, implementing fair investigation processes, and administering appropriate penalties when misconduct is confirmed. By maintaining consistency in addressing academic dishonesty, instructors send a strong message that dishonest behavior will not be tolerated and that academic integrity is a non-negotiable expectation (Burgason et al., 2019).

In conclusion, establishing clear expectations for academic integrity and outlining the repercussions of academic dishonesty are critical components in promoting a culture of academic integrity in asynchronous language teaching. By effectively communicating these expectations, informing students of the consequences, and consistently enforcing the established policies, instructors can create a learning environment that upholds the values of integrity, fosters ethical behavior, and empowers students to take pride in their own academic achievements.

Promoting Academic Integrity through Collaboration.

Promoting collaboration among students in asynchronous language teaching is not only a pedagogical approach but also an effective strategy to cultivate academic integrity within the virtual learning environment (Jang, 2017). By providing opportunities for peer learning and fostering a sense of community, collaboration reduces the incentive for academic dishonesty and creates a more conducive and supportive academic environment.

Collaborative learning activities in asynchronous language teaching offer numerous benefits that contribute to the promotion of academic integrity. Firstly, collaboration encourages active student engagement, which can reduce the motivation for students to resort to cheating. When students actively participate in collaborative tasks, such as group discussions, project-

based assignments, or peer reviews, they become more invested in their own learning process. This increased engagement not only reduces the temptation to engage in dishonest practices but also promotes a genuine desire to contribute meaningfully to the shared learning experience.

Moreover, collaborative learning fosters a sense of community and support among students. By working together towards common goals, students develop a stronger connection with their peers, leading to a shared responsibility for upholding academic integrity. In a collaborative environment, students are more likely to hold each other accountable for their actions and encourage ethical behavior. The establishment of a supportive learning community where students value and respect one another's contributions creates a positive academic atmosphere where academic integrity is nurtured and celebrated (Liu et al., 2021).

Collaborative learning activities also provide an avenue for peer learning, which further enhances academic integrity. Through collaborative tasks, students have the opportunity to learn from their peers, share diverse perspectives, and collectively construct knowledge. This peer-to-peer learning approach promotes a deeper understanding of the subject matter and encourages critical thinking and problem-solving skills. When students are actively engaged in learning from and with their peers, the need for dishonest practices, such as plagiarism or cheating, diminishes as they recognize the value of authentic engagement and the mutual benefit of knowledge exchange.

To effectively promote collaboration and academic integrity, instructors can incorporate various strategies and tools into their asynchronous language teaching practices. For instance, they can create structured group activities that encourage active participation and equal contribution from all group members. Utilizing online collaboration platforms and discussion boards can provide a space for students to collaborate virtually, share ideas, and engage in meaningful dialogue. Instructors can also establish clear guidelines and expectations for collaborative work, emphasizing the importance of mutual respect, active participation, and the acknowledgment of individual and group contributions.

In conclusion, promoting collaboration among students in asynchronous language teaching serves as a powerful means to foster academic integrity. By providing opportunities for peer learning, reducing the incentive for academic dishonesty, and creating a supportive academic environment, collaboration contributes to the cultivation of a culture of integrity. Through structured collaborative activities and the establishment of clear expectations, instructors can empower students to engage authentically, value the contributions of others, and uphold the principles of academic integrity in their virtual learning journeys.

Promoting Academic Integrity through the Cultivation of Academic Honesty.

Encouraging academic honesty through discussions of the importance of academic integrity and the provision of relevant resources is a crucial component

of promoting a culture of integrity in asynchronous language teaching (Chiang et al., 2022). By engaging students in conversations about ethical behavior, instilling a sense of pride in their own work, and offering valuable resources, instructors can foster an environment where academic integrity is valued and upheld.

Discussions centered around the significance of academic integrity serve as a powerful tool to promote ethical behavior among students. By engaging in open dialogues about the principles of academic honesty, instructors can raise awareness about the detrimental consequences of academic dishonesty and highlight the value of integrity in academic settings. These discussions can provide students with a deeper understanding of the ethical implications of their actions and help them develop a sense of responsibility towards their own learning journey and the scholarly community at large.

Furthermore, these discussions create an opportunity for instructors to emphasize the importance of taking pride in one's own work. By encouraging students to appreciate the intrinsic value of their efforts, instructors can nurture a sense of ownership and personal investment in their academic pursuits. Students who recognize the significance of their contributions are more likely to engage in authentic and original work, reducing the inclination to resort to dishonest practices. Instilling a sense of pride in their accomplishments helps students develop a strong ethical foundation and promotes a culture of academic integrity (Wiley, 2022).

In addition to discussions, providing resources such as writing and study skill workshops plays a vital role in supporting students' academic development and integrity. These workshops equip students with the necessary skills to engage in academic work with integrity, including proper citation practices, effective research techniques, and critical thinking strategies. By offering resources tailored to the specific needs of asynchronous language teaching, instructors empower students to navigate the challenges of the virtual learning environment with integrity and confidence. Access to these resources ensures that students have the tools and knowledge to produce high-quality work and make informed ethical decisions throughout their academic journey.

Moreover, instructors can leverage technology to enhance the availability and accessibility of these resources. Online platforms, learning management systems, and digital libraries can serve as repositories for resources, making them easily accessible to students at any time. By utilizing these technological tools, instructors can ensure that students have continuous access to academic support, promoting a culture of integrity that is not bound by time or location.

In conclusion, encouraging academic honesty through discussions of the importance of academic integrity and the provision of resources is a vital component of promoting academic integrity in asynchronous language teaching. By engaging students in conversations about ethical behavior, fostering pride in their own work, and providing relevant resources, instructors can create an environment where integrity is valued,

upheld, and celebrated. These efforts contribute to the development of responsible and ethical learners who actively engage in their academic pursuits with integrity, thus nurturing a culture of academic excellence and integrity in asynchronous language teaching settings.

Conclusions.

Educators in Ukraine have faced numerous challenges while teaching during the pandemic and war. However, these difficulties have also highlighted the resilience and adaptability of the Ukrainian educational community. Despite these challenges, educators have shown ingenuity in developing creative and effective methods for facilitating remote learning. They have demonstrated unwavering commitment to ensuring that every student has access to high-quality education, regardless of the obstacles they face. While asynchronous learning has proven to be a valuable tool in supporting education in Ukraine, proper organization on the principles of academic integrity is crucial for maximizing its effectiveness. There are still various obstacles and gaps that need to be addressed to ensure an engaging and effective learning experience. It is important to conduct further investigation and implement remedies to address concerns related to academic integrity, as it plays a vital role in maintaining academic excellence.

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